

Validation of a Two-Step Neutronics Workflow using Gnat and OpenMC with the ZED-2 Research Reactor

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ABSTRACT

Gnat is a deterministic transport code developed at Ontario Tech University. A validation of a coupled OpenMC/Gnat workflow is presented using the ZED-2 criticality benchmarks published by Atomic Energy of Canada Limited in 2012. OpenMC was used to generate a library of multi-group cross-sections for each material in the ZED-2 reactor using CASMO-2/4/8 energy structures. The error associated with energy discretizations was quantified and compared to continuous-energy OpenMC computations. Gnat was used to calculate values of k_{eff} for the reactor which served as a basis for comparison with benchmark solutions. Equivalent constructive solid geometry and meshed representations of the reactor geometry were created to support this. Initial computation using the CASMO-2 energy structure and isotropic scattering yielded disagreement with an error of 3024 pcm between continuous and multi-group OpenMC results; applying the CASMO-8 energy structure and a transport correction for scattering yielded good agreement with an error of only 142 pcm. Deterministic transport with Gnat showed excellent agreement with the OpenMC results using the CASMO-8 energy structure having an error of -63 pcm and 73 pcm for the multi-group and continuous-energy runs respectively. Sources of error were discussed, and spatial discretization in the Gnat solution was determined to be the dominant contributor based on analysis of the flux solutions.

Keywords: Neutronics, Workflow, Gnat, OpenMC, ZED-2

1. INTRODUCTION

Reactor physics codes are broadly classified into two categories based on their approach to solving the Boltzmann transport equation: deterministic methods, and stochastic methods. Recent advances in high performance computing have enabled the use of Monte Carlo (MC) methods in more areas of reactor analysis including multi-physics analysis. However, deterministic transport methods remain the preferred approach where performance is paramount and some solution accuracy can be sacrificed to discretization error. This trade-off is common in the transient analysis of reactors and design iteration. A universal disadvantage of deterministic transport methods is the need for multi-group cross sections (MGXSs). These cross sections can either be generated ahead of time in the form of a MGXS library (the "two step" method), or generated on-the-fly at runtime. Several MC codes come with existing MGXS generation capabilities, including the free and open source (FOSS) OpenMC project [1]. This typically provides users with a framework that facilitates the generation and export of custom MGXS libraries for use with a deterministic solvers, such as DRAGON5 [2], Griffin [3], or Moltres [4].

The General Neutral particle Analysis Toolkit (Gnat) is a FOSS deterministic transport solver developed at Ontario Tech University based on the INL Multiphysics Object-Oriented Simulation Environment (MOOSE) framework. It has previously been used to analyze the proposed Ontario Tech Subcritical Assembly [5], which uses a fuel similar in material composition and design to the fuel of the Zero Energy Deuterium (ZED-2) Reactor at Canadian Nuclear Laboratories in Chalk River. To build upon

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previous simulation work, this paper provides validation of Gnat with two-step methodology coupling OpenMC applied to the ZED-2 reactor benchmark.

The remainder of this work is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the ZED-2 benchmark problem. Section 3 describes the computational approach taken in this work for MGXS generation with OpenMC and deterministic transport with Gnat. Section 4 presents the results of the validation efforts for OpenMC and Gnat, and Section 5 presents some concluding remarks and areas for future work.

2. THE ZERO ENERGY DEUTERIUM (ZED-2) REACTOR

The ZED-2 reactor is a heavy-water moderated tank-type research reactor located in Chalk River, Ontario, Canada [6]. Criticality was first reached in 1960 and it has been used in a variety of experimental work since. The core is situated within an open-top aluminum calandria and is surrounded by a graphite reflector. Fuel and absorber rods are suspended from steel hangers over the core, providing flexibility in terms of lattice spacing and structure. The depth of the moderator can be adjusted to reach criticality as needed. In 2012, a suite of neutronics benchmarks based on the ZED-2 reactor was published [6]. The report included an uncertainty analysis of select geometry, presentation of atom densities and impurities, and all other information necessary to model and simulate three experimentally-critical reactor configurations. Two models were provided for the benchmark; a more-detailed version with minimal changes from the real-world geometry, and a simplified version excluding various features that have little impact on the results. The published benchmark provides a series of MCNP 5 sample calculations which show good agreement with the experimental k_{eff} . An overview of the simplified geometry from the benchmark is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Simplified benchmark overview.

The reactor configuration for the benchmark uses a hexagonal lattice of 91 pins with a lattice pitch and moderator depth dependent on which case is being studied. The lattice pitch ranges from 22.86 cm to 20.00 cm with a respective moderator depth of 167.520 cm to 155.849 cm; the geometry for each case is the result of measuring a real-world experimentally critical configuration. The remaining features such as the reflector, calandria, and dump lines are constant for all cases. A considerable amount of detail is still in the simplified benchmark. The calandria wall is relatively thin (0.635 cm) compared to

the scale of the benchmark, and has a small layer of air separating it and the reflector. The cladding has small features including a flange at the top and cutout at the bottom. This affects other bodies that surround the cladding, specifically the rod end caps, shown in blue in Figure 2. This is not particularly challenging for constructive solid geometry (CSG) commonly used in MC transport codes, but proves suboptimal when generating a mesh for use with Gnat. Accurately meshing the reactor when the scale of features varies by several orders of magnitudes requires significant changes in mesh element size across the geometry and generally increases the difficulty in creating a high-quality mesh.

Figure 2. Rod-level benchmark details [cm].

3. COMPUTATIONAL METHODOLOGY

The first step of the neutronics workflow utilized in this work is the modeling of the ZED-2 research reactor in OpenMC running in continuous energy mode. This allows for the validation of OpenMC against the publicly available benchmark data while simultaneously generating MGXS for use in Gnat. After the continuous energy features of OpenMC are validated, the generated MGXS are validated by running OpenMC in multi-group mode. This isolates any remaining bias in the deterministic solution of ZED-2 using said MGXS to the space-angle discretization and the deterministic transport solver itself. Finally, the MGXS library is used to simulate ZED-2 in Gnat. The remainder of this section focuses on the specifics of cross-section generation and verification with OpenMC, and the details of the modeling performed with Gnat. The full set of input decks and data files described in this section can be found at <https://github.com/OTU-Centre-for-SMRs/zed-2>.

3.1. Cross Section Generation with OpenMC

All three cases of the simplified ZED-2 benchmark problem were modeled in OpenMC using CSG for the purpose of validating OpenMC against the provided critical configurations. The ENDF-VII.0 continuous energy cross section library [7] was initially used to compare continuous energy results with the MCNP reference solutions and the parametric uncertainties provided by the benchmark [6]. This is followed with simulations using the more established ENDF-VII.1 cross section library [8] to generate MGXS for the multi-group OpenMC and Gnat calculations. All continuous energy and multi-group OpenMC calculations used the same simulation parameters: 10000 active batches, 1000 inactive batches (determined suitable by assessing fission source convergence via Shannon entropy), and 100000 particles per batch.

MGXS are generated using the CASMO-2, CASMO-4, and CASMO-8 group structures which are com-

monly used for the analysis of light water reactor (LWR) systems [9]. These group structures are considered sufficient for this validation work as the spectral characteristics of the ZED-2 reactor are similar to those of other thermal reactor systems. In addition to the group boundaries and number of groups, the anisotropy of the scattering cross-sections has a non-negligible impact on k_{eff} in low atomic mass systems [10]. Therefore P_0 , P_0 transport corrected, and P_1 scattering cross-sections will be tested. The transport corrected cross sections use the in-scatter approximation. Finally, the low-leakage nature of the ZED-2 core motivates the preliminary use of per-material homogenization when generating MGXS. In future work, we aim to investigate higher fidelity cross section homogenization approaches to confirm the validity of this approach.

3.2. Deterministic Transport with Gnat

Gnat is a discrete ordinates (S_N) transport solver which discretizes and solves the self-adjoint angular flux (SAAF) form of the neutron transport equation with the continuous finite element method (CFEM) [5]. The full sparse matrix system for the entire transport equation is assembled for all energy, angular, and spatial degrees of freedom (DOFs). The spatial discretization and solution scheme employed by Gnat imposes several limitations on the mesh that can be used to represent the geometry, as the SAAF method is prone to negativities and spurious oscillations near strong discontinuities. Additionally, the full matrix assemblage performed by Gnat is highly memory and compute intensive, which limits the number of total DOFs that can be utilized. To minimize the number of angular DOFs, a reduced order Gauss-Chebyshev product quadrature with 36 directions per octant was utilized. This is considered valid in this work as the angular flux is diffuse in all energy groups in the ZED-2 reactor, and so ray effects (a defect of the S_N method) will not be the dominant error mode compared to energy and spatial discretization error. Reflective boundary conditions are applied on the x-z plane at $y = 0$ cm to simulate a half-core; vacuum boundary conditions are applied on all remaining faces.

A CAD model was prepared identical to the CSG OpenMC model of ZED-2. Coreform Cubit was used to create an Exodus-II mesh compatible with Gnat to simulate the reactor. It consisted of mixed hex, tet, and pyramid elements generated with various meshing algorithms. Special care was taken to incorporate hex-meshing in the entire fueled core region to limit the number of spatial DOFs, resulting in a mesh with approximately 700 000 elements. No additional homogenization or simplification was performed on the benchmark geometry for transport with Gnat; a convergence study for the spatial and angular discretization was not included as part of this work. Linear Lagrange CFEM basis functions were used to further limit the number of spatial DOFs. Some details of the mesh are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Deterministic transport mesh used in Gnat.

4. RESULTS

The first step in the two-step validation workflow is the validation of the OpenMC ZED-2 model through comparisons with the exactly critical experimental configurations. In addition to providing comparisons with the experimental k_{eff} of unity, the MCNP results obtained by [6] are referenced for code-to-code verification. The results for each criticality experiment (cases one to three) can be found in Table I for the ENDF-VII.0 and ENDF-VII.1 cross section libraries. These are compared to the MCNP reference solutions obtained by [6], which used ENDF-VII.0 cross sections. The parametric uncertainties in Table I were determined by sampling material properties and dimensions within 1σ measurement uncertainties, running many criticality calculations in MCNP to obtain total uncertainty for each experimental configuration [6]. The continuous energy OpenMC simulations agree quite well with the experimental k_{eff} and the MCNP reference solutions for each criticality experiment. All OpenMC results fall within the 1σ parametric uncertainty provided by [6], with ENDF-VII.1 performing slightly better for all three experiments than ENDF-VII.0. Due to the minimal differences between each criticality experiment, case one was picked for cross section generation and the validation of Gnat using the ENDF-VII.1 library.

Table I. OpenMC continuous energy results for each benchmark problem. MCNP results and parametric uncertainty are obtained from [6].

Case	Fuel Pitch [cm]	Critical D ₂ O Height [cm]	OpenMC k_{eff} ENDF-VII.0 $\pm 3\sigma$ [pcm]	OpenMC k_{eff} ENDF-VII.1 $\pm 3\sigma$ [pcm]	MCNP k_{eff} $\pm 3\sigma$ [pcm]	1σ Parametric Uncertainty [pcm]
1	22.86	167.520	1.00140 \pm 9	1.00103 \pm 9	1.00211 \pm 18	326
2	20.00	155.849	1.00126 \pm 9	1.00112 \pm 9	1.00206 \pm 18	323
3	21.59	166.720	1.00126 \pm 9	1.00109 \pm 9	1.00211 \pm 15	323

With the continuous energy model of the ZED-2 reactor validated, the group constants can be generated and verified. Results of this verification procedure can be found in Table II. In general, the bias on the eigenvalue (compared to the continuous energy model) decreases as one subdivides the energy spectrum. However, the largest improvements in Δk_{eff} are obtained when also increasing the order of the scattering treatment. Isotropic scattering cross sections are insufficient for modeling the ZED-2 reactor due to highly forward-peaked scattering inherent to D₂O moderated systems. Applying a transport correction results in a substantial improvement over isotropic scattering cross sections, even compared to linear anisotropic scattering. Given the convergence penalty inherent to higher order scattering corrections in S_N solvers [10], isotropic and transport corrected isotropic scattering cross sections are selected for the final verification and validation of Gnat. Future work should investigate modifications to the CASMO-8 group structure to further improve the 142 pcm bias obtained during cross section verification without adding additional DOFs to the problem.

Table II. OpenMC multi-group results for case 1. $\Delta k_{\text{eff}} = k_{\text{eff,MG}} - k_{\text{eff,CE}}$.

Group Structure	Scattering Treatment								
	P ₀			P ₀ Corrected			P ₁		
	k_{eff}	3σ [pcm]	Δk_{eff} [pcm]	k_{eff}	3σ [pcm]	Δk_{eff} [pcm]	k_{eff}	3σ [pcm]	Δk_{eff} [pcm]
CASMO-2	1.03127	6	3024	1.01208	6	1105	1.01414	6	1311
CASMO-4	1.02653	6	2550	1.00624	6	521	1.00746	6	643
CASMO-8	1.02385	6	2282	1.00245	6	142	1.00365	6	262

Results from the S_N calculations in Gnat have been summarized in Table III, where the biases in the

solution are computed against the continuous energy and multi-group OpenMC results in Table I and Table II. Given the minimal number of directions used and the coarse mesh in the reflector, Gnat performs quite well compared to the multi-group OpenMC reference. The maximum bias with multi-group OpenMC was -273 pcm (CASMO-4 with P_0 cross sections), and the minimum bias was -46 pcm. Refinement of the group structure and use of transport corrected scattering cross sections yielded a bias of 73 pcm with the continuous energy OpenMC reference solution, which is surprising given that multi-group OpenMC resulted in a bias of 142 pcm. It is likely that the better agreement obtained with Gnat is due to cancellation of error between the finite element spatial discretization and the S_N method.

Table III. Gnat multi-group results for case 1. $\Delta k_{\text{eff}} = k_{\text{eff,Gnat}} - k_{\text{eff,OpenMC}}$.

Group Structure	Scattering Treatment					
	P_0			P_0 Corrected		
	k_{eff}	$\Delta k_{\text{eff,MG}}$ [pcm]	$\Delta k_{\text{eff,CE}}$ [pcm]	k_{eff}	$\Delta k_{\text{eff,MG}}$ [pcm]	$\Delta k_{\text{eff,CE}}$ [pcm]
CASMO-2	1.03081	-46	2978	1.01300	92	1197
CASMO-4	1.02380	-273	2277	1.00502	-122	399
CASMO-8	1.02164	-221	2061	1.00182	-63	73

Figure 4 presents the axial distribution of three different flux groups along the reflective boundary condition using the CASMO-8 group structure and isotropic cross sections. Negative fluxes can be found in all scalar flux groups, indicating that the mesh discretization employed in this work is insufficient to capture angular flux gradients and cross section heterogeneities. Spatial discretization error resulting in negative fluxes is particularly prominent in the fast group due to the highly thermal spectrum of the ZED-2 reactor and the large void region with near-zero cross sections in the fast group. Artificial upwind diffusion is added to the solution in this region to stabilize the SAAF equations. This, combined with the severe jump discontinuity between air and cladding, likely resulted in additional spatial discretization error above the moderator for group 1.

Figure 4. Fluxes from Gnat [$n/(cm^2 \cdot s)$]. Sliced along the y - z reflective boundary condition, bisecting the core. Scalar fluxes are normalized to a total fission power of 1 W.

Figure 5 presents the radial distribution of the group 1, 3 and 8 scalar fluxes using the CASMO-8 group

structure with isotropic scattering cross sections. Similar to Figure 4, negative scalar fluxes can be found in all energy groups, although their presence is exaggerated through the use of a non-logarithmic colour scale. On this radial plane star-shaped spatial artifacts in the fast flux can be seen which are caused by the choice of meshing approach used in the fuel (to enable swept hex meshing). Similar artifacts can be seen in the group 8 flux, indicating that alternative meshing schemes (such as the MOOSE Reactor module [11]) should be investigated in the highly absorbing fuel region to minimize the presence of negative scalar flux solutions. Higher fidelity MGXS homogenization schemes, such as per-cell homogenization with distributed cell filters, may also prove effective in decreasing the jump discontinuity between different homogenized regions.

Figure 5. Fluxes from Gnat [$n/(cm^2 \cdot s)$]. x - y cutting plane taken 100 cm above the +0 datum in Figure 1b. Scalar fluxes are normalized to a total fission power of 1 W.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented the validation of a two-step workflow with the ZED-2 experimental reactor, where the open-source MC code OpenMC is used to generate cross sections for the S_N solver Gnat. Three critical configurations of ZED-2 were simulated to validate the OpenMC model, where the largest deviation from criticality simulated by OpenMC was 140 pcm (well within the 1σ parametric uncertainty determined by the benchmark authors). MGXS were then generated and verified for the first critical configuration; the best agreement was obtained with a per-material homogenization, the CASMO-8 group structure, and transport corrected scattering cross sections. Validation of Gnat shows a minimum bias on k_{eff} of -63 pcm (with multi-group OpenMC) and 73 pcm (continuous energy OpenMC). An analysis of the scalar flux distributions predicted by Gnat for several energy groups indicate that dominant error mode in the deterministic solution is spatial discretization error. We consider these validation results to be preliminary as k_{eff} is prone to cancellation of error, and aim to extend the validation base with activation foils should data become available in the future. Additional future work should include: geometric simplifications to ease the deterministic modeling burden of the ZED-2 benchmark, parametric mesh generation with the MOOSE Reactor module to decrease spatial discretization error, and further validation of Gnat with cases two and three. An additional area of future work is the investigation of higher fidelity MGXS homogenization, down to the level of per-element cross sections. The infrastructure has been recently added to the multi-physics driver application Cardinal [12] to enable the generation of these high fidelity cross sections (https://cardinal.cels.anl.gov/tutorials/openmc_mgxs.html); an example of per-cell MGXS (applied to ZED-2 reactor) can be found in Figure 6.

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Figure 6. Mesh-based 2-group MGXS generated by Cardinal over the moderator.

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